

STUDY HABITS OF ADOLESCENTS IN RELATION TO GENDER, LOCALE AND STREAM OF STUDY

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ABSTRACT:

This research aims to explore study habits of adolescents studying in senior secondary schools. Furthermore an attempt has been made to see whether any difference exists between their study habits in relation to Gender, Locale and Stream of study. The sample included total 100 students of 10+2 class. Stratified random sampling was used to select the respondents, study habits inventory by Dr. N.S Yadav was used for data collection. Significant difference between the study habits of adolescents in relation to Gender and Locale has been found. No significant difference has been found between the study habits of adolescents having science and art stream.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern scientific and technological world education plays a pivotal role. Education system as a whole is expected to prepare the younger generation to adapt better in the dynamic society. Education not only fills the missing links and gaps created due to fast paced life but also creates general awareness about the changing scenario. Education is the axis around which revolves the fullness of the human being. Thus, education is an indispensable instrument for stability and progress of the individual as well as society.

In order to proceed towards the attainment of goal, one must engage oneself in a variety of intellectual activities called “studying” study habits are related to the study behavior of an individual. It involves both teaching and learning process. Effective learning not only depends on good teaching but also on satisfactory learning procedures i.e. good study habits. Study habits are habitual way of exercising and practicing the abilities for learning. Psychologists and educationists believe that good study habits are the gateways to knowledge and wisdom. It is one of the effective means of systematic development of knowledge, language and personality of an individual.

STUDY HABITS

Study habits have been defined as the sum total of all habits of determined purposes and enforced practices that the individual uses in order to learn. It is necessary for the students to develop special study habits and skills. A well formed habit furnishes its own sources of motivation As such the word ‘Study habits’ comprised of two words: ‘study’ and ‘habits’. According to English and English *habit is an acquired act, usually relatively simple one that is regularly or customarily manifested and study is relatively protracted application to a topic or problems for the purpose of learning about the topic. Solving the problem or memorizing part or all to the presented material.* Study habits are the pupils or students way of studying whether systematic or unsystematic, efficient or inefficient etc. When a student divides the requirements for his study and regularly follows it could be called study habits.

Patel (1976) analyses seven study habits-

- Home environment and planning of work
- Reading and note taking habits
- Planning of subjects
- Habits of concentration

- Preparation for examination
- General habits and attitudes
- School or College environment

According to **Azikiwe (1998)** *Study habits are learning tendencies that enable students to work privately*. Thus study habit implies a sort of more or less permanent method of studying. It is the end product of activity engagement. People have their own way of studying, some study with a definite plans and programmes of studies. Some believe in the habit of starting their studies one to two months before the examination. Some believe in the habit of memorization and some believe in regularity, punctuality and proper planning. So from this we know that there are so many habits of studying.

NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Adolescence is the period of career selection. The child has to make decision about the subjects he wants to study. In the present era of globalization, there is fierce competition in every sphere of life. On academic side, there is no place anywhere for the average and below average students. Excellence in the academic achievement becomes the pre requisite for each career what so ever it may be. In the field of education, a burning problem is the constant increase in the number of failures at the school level. The failure rate in various examinations may depend on many factors but one of the main reason is poor or ineffective study habits. Now days students do not devote sufficient time to their studies and seldom have proper study habits.

Scholastic underachievement and failure have caused serious concern to educationists, guidance counselors and educational planners for several decades as this amount to colossal wastage of resources available for education. It is felt that students with good study habits are better than others. It is important to have a clear understanding of what benefits or hinders one's educational achievement. This is the premise on which this study is justified The study habits of learners depend upon the learner's ability to schedule his time, the plan of his study, the habits of concentration, note taking, mental review, over learning, massed and distributed learning and so on.

The problem of study habits is one of immense importance both form the theoretical and practical point of view. Theoretically efficient learning depends upon the development of efficient study habits and skills and as such one of the continuous objectives of teaching should be the improvement of study habits and skills of the students. From the practical point of view, the problem is all the more important. Very often, teachers come across such students who appear to have above average scholastic aptitude, yet they are doing very poorly in their courses of study. A large majority of these seem to have faulty-study habits. Proper guidance can change their faulty study habits into desirable ones. This study intends to investigate Study habits of adolescents in relation to Gender, Locale and Stream of study. So that Proper guidance can be given to them who have poor study habits.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Study habits of adolescents in relation to Gender, Locale and Stream of study.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

The objectives of the study were as follows.

1. To study the difference between study habits of boys and girls adolescents.
2. To study the difference between study habits of rural and urban adolescents.
3. To study the difference between study habits of adolescents having science and arts stream.

HYPOTHESES

As per the objectives of study, the present study was undertaken to test the following hypotheses.

1. There is no significant difference between the study habits of adolescent boys and girls.

2. There is no significant difference between the study habits of rural and urban adolescents.
3. There is no significant difference between study habits of adolescents having science and arts stream.

DESIGN OF THE STUDY

In the present study, descriptive survey method was employed to investigate the study habits of adolescents in relation to Gender, Locale and Stream of study.

SAMPLE

The study was conducted on 100 students (50 boys and 50 girls) having science and arts stream of 10+2 class which were randomly selected from rural and urban senior secondary schools of Ludhiana District.

TOOL USED

Study Habits Inventory by Dr. N.S Yadav was used for data collection.

DESCRIPTION OF THE TEST

The inventory comprises 125 items pertaining to lie in sub-components namely planning (25 items), reading (25 items) note-taking (25 items), revision (25 items) and examination (25 items) which characterize the basic of study habits. The items have been drafted in affirmative (74) and negative (51) forms. Scores given for positive items were 3,2,1 for responses ‘always’, ‘sometimes’ and ‘never’ respectively, whereas the scoring process was reversed as 1,2,3 for ‘always’, ‘sometimes’ and ‘never’ respectively, in case of negative items.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

Mean, S.D and t-test were used for analysis of data.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF THE DATA

Table 1 Difference between study habits of adolescent boys and girls

Category	No. of students	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio
Boys	50	212.44	18.42	6.14 Significant at 0.01 level
Girls	50	239.12	24.69	

Table 1 shows that the mean score of study habits of boys is 212.44 with S.D. as 18.42 and mean score of girls on study habits is 239.12 with S.D. as 24.69. The mean score of study habits of girls is higher than the mean score of study habits of boys. The value of t-ratio is 6.14 which is significant at 0.01 level. So it is found that study habits of girls are better than the study habits of boys. Hence the hypothesis that there is no significant difference between study habits of boys and girls is rejected. Reason for the above mentioned results may be due to the fact that girls are still discriminated against boys in our society. They get fewer opportunities than boys. So they work hard than boys. They leave no chance of losing the opportunity.

Table 2 Difference between study habits of rural and urban adolescents

Category	No. of students	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio
Rural	50	216.16	20.62	4.06 Significant at 0.01 level
Urban	50	235.4	26.42	

Table 2 shows that the mean score of study habits of rural students is 216.16 with S.D. as 20.62 and mean score of urban students is 235.4 with S.D. as 26.42. The mean score of study habits of urban

students is higher than the mean score of study habits of rural students. The value t-ratio is 4.06 which is significant at 0.01 level. So it can be concluded that study habits of urban student are significantly better than the study habits of rural students. Hence the hypothesis that there is no significant difference between study habits of rural and urban adolescents is rejected.

Reason for the above mentioned results may be due to the fact that in villages, population density is less as compared to cities. In cities the dwelling units are closer, the adolescents observe the study habits of others and they relate a particular system of study with achievement and follow the best one. Moreover in urban areas, there are enormous study centers and libraries for the students.

Table 3 Difference between study habits of science and arts stream adolescents

Category	No. of students	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio
Science	50	227.64	24.50	0.39
Arts	50	223.92	26.54	N.S

From table 3 it can be seen that the mean score of science students is 227.64 with S.D. as 24.50 and mean score of arts students is 223.92 with S.D. as 26.54. The mean score of science students is slightly higher than the mean score of arts students. The t-ratio is 0.39 which is not significant. Hence the difference is attributed to chance factor alone. Therefore the hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the study habits of science and arts stream adolescents is accepted.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. There is significant difference between the study habits of adolescent boys and girls.
2. There is significant difference between the study habits of rural and urban adolescents.
3. There is no significant difference between the study habits of adolescents having science and arts stream.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

The present investigation was limited to 10+2 class students. Attempts can be made to investigate the study habits of students studying in degree colleges, vocational colleges and universities. Relationship of study habits with intelligence and achievement of adolescents can be studied. Effect of home environment and use of social media on study habits can be studied. Relationship between parental involvement and study habits of college students can also be taken up. The effect of peer group on the study habits can be another area of research.

CONCLUSION

In present days, for academic excellence as well as for the personal development, a pupil must have good study habits. Proper study habits should be inculcated and nurtured at the very young age of the child. Efforts should be made both by the parents as well as by the school authorities to provide congenial environment to develop good habits among the children.

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